

DESIGNING INCLUSIVE USABILITY EXPERIENCES: BEST PRACTICES FOR
ACCOMMODATING NEURODIVERSE USERS

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Abstract

This paper explores the use of inclusive design in augmenting inclusive experience for neurodivergent populations typically people with autistic, ADHD, and dyslexic disabilities. It elaborates on how a poorly designed inclusive experience might bring on stress, anxiety, or total disengagement from their use. The paper zeroes in on the customizations at sensory levels and cognitive-friendly layouts in the proposition on how to make inclusive experience more accessible and empowering. In the application of the Social Model of Disability, it says it is an emphasis on the recognition that inclusive design can eliminate obstacles in inclusive experience and can foster innovation, accessibility and equity.

Index Terms—Neurodiverse, ADA, Neurodivergent, WCAG, Accessibility, Usability, ADHD

I. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

In the technological evolving sphere, the holistic approach towards the way individuals interact with technology and maintain their mental, emotional, and physical health while interacting with online platforms. For neurodivergent people, such as people with autistic, ADHD, dyslexia related disabilities, the online experience is more of a hindrance or facilitator of accessibility if they are designed inclusively [1]. Some of the challenges neurodivergent individuals undergo include not being able to process information easily, experiencing sensory overload, and distractions by certain online layouts and interfaces. When not well-designed, these experiences may lead to stress, anxiety and disengagement and, therefore, affect their overall usability. For example, people with sensory sensitivity and cognitive problems may find difficult navigation, cluttered writing, or bright, flashing visuals overwhelming [2].

Integrating inclusive design principles is necessary for building and enhancing inclusive experience among neurodivergent users and it also accommodates a large range of sensory and cognitive needs. Expected best practices include simplification of the user interface, providing options for users to customize settings such as color contrasts, text sizes, adjustable brightness, flashings, movements and reducing sensory distractions [3]. Ensuring easy navigation with

minimal ambiguity, alternative input methods such as keyboard commands or voice commands, and providing content in various media formats such as audio, video or text can also upgrade accessibility. The strategies for inclusive design also include neurodivergent users in the phase of development as well as testing so that online spaces are created keeping their needs in view. This would foster a setting where they are not hindered by unnecessary obstacles [4]. Such approaches promote inclusive experience and also fall under the broader objective of equity and comprehensive inclusion.

1.2 Research Aim

The study's aim is to the best practices and principles for designing comprehensive, accessible experiences specifically for neurodivergent people, concentrating on how user-centred design mainly can accommodate distinct neurodiverse people and support various cognitive requirements.

1.3 Research Objectives

- To clarify and define key neurodivergence concepts and examine its prevalence and effect on the interaction of individuals with online content as well as interfaces.
- To explore the issues dealt by neurodivergent people when interacting specifically with new modern settings, involving websites, online platforms and apps.
- To determine best practices or strategies for user-centred design that focus on inclusivity, ease of use and accessibility for neurodivergent people with different cognitive abilities.
- To analyze existing inclusive experience tactics and assess their effectiveness mainly in addressing the neurodivergent users' needs across distinct platforms.
- To investigate techniques for strengthening compassion in the design procedure, motivating teams of design to incorporate neurodivergent views into the digital content as well as experiences development.
- To give suggestions for upgrading online access, particularly through design tools, practical strategies and guidelines that aid in creating more inclusive and accessible digital settings for neurodivergent people.

1.4 Significance

In today's world, inclusive experience has implications for accessibility, inclusivity, and equity in a significantly digitized world, especially for people with disabilities, but more so for neurodivergent users. Since technology pervades nearly all aspects of life, in particular, work, learning, socialization, and entertainment, ensuring that online spaces meet the needs of diverse users will become an important necessity. Inadequately designed online settings can present additional barriers, avoidable for individuals with neurodiverse conditions who feel isolated, anxious, and frustrated [5]. A focus on developing inclusive design strategies that place emphasis on accessibility and friendly interfaces ensures that the online platform empowers rather than excludes these users from improving their accessibility to asserting an equal right to take part in society without unnecessary technological barriers.

Inclusive design is also extremely important for businesses and organizations wanting to serve a diverse and wide user base. Though the consideration given to neurodivergent users and other

users with disabilities might reach very limited target audiences, otherwise companies would be able to expand their reach to more potential users and increase overall satisfaction [6]. Fostering inclusivity creates economic and social benefits in that it assists in bridging the digital divide, which can lead to better mental health outcomes among vulnerable populations. Affirming experiences to become inclusive also lines up with increasing global standards as well as legislation mainly around accessibility, including Web Content Accessibility Guidelines (WCAG). Enhancement of inclusive experience for individuals with disabilities is not just social and ethical accountability but a practical, long-term opportunity for sustainable innovation as well as inclusion in the new evolving environment.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Neurodivergence is a term for natural differences in cognitive processing and interaction in conditions like autism, ADHD and dyslexia. Online environments are often designed with an eye to neurotypical users' needs but can be quite demanding for neurodivergent people-for instance, sensory overload or navigation. Therefore, inclusive design, catering to these needs, enhances their ability to access and interact with digital content as well as platforms.

2.1 Key Concepts of Neurodivergence and Its Impact on Online Interactions

Neurodivergence means that there's natural variance in the way human brains function- think of it as the difference in style, techniques, and mechanism from that of the neurotypical norm. This includes autism, ADHD, dyslexia, dyspraxia, as well as Tourette syndrome. Neurodiverse people mostly differ in ways of processing sensory input, focus, memory, and ways of making sense of different messages. Such differences can make them respond differently to stimuli cognitively and behaviourally [7]. Such diversity challenges the normative values embedded in society and calls for the development of settings be they physical or digital that accommodate and respect these differences. Much content and interface design assume a generic user experience, inadvertently neglecting neurodiverse needs and erecting exclusionary barriers to large sections of the populace. Neurodivergence is growingly perceived as a condition that affects 15-20% of the general population determined as neurodivergent. As such, people in this category interact differently with digital content. People with ADHD, for example, cannot focus on chaotic or too distracting digital environments, while those on the autism spectrum will find an interface that lacks predictability and structure unhelpful [8]. These differences in engagement, therefore, clearly state that there is a strong requirement for setting the online interfaces to suit the varied cognitive abilities of a person. If these requirements are not met, neurodivergent individuals would perceive a heightened level of stress and frustration as exclusion from accessing content through online platforms might reduce access towards crucial information and services available [9].

2.2 Issues Dealt with by Neurodivergent Individuals in Technological Environments

When dealing with digital settings, especially websites, applications, or online communities, neurodivergent people may experience sensory overload due to an excessive number of visual or

aural stimuli, including flashing advertisements, loud noises, and brilliant colour schemes [0]. For those whose senses are highly magnified, this could cause difficulty and discomfort or anxiety for the user. Moreover, many of these online tools are designed from a linear, step-by-step perspective for work completion, which may be at odds with the way people with ADHD tend to think, often having trouble keeping sustained attention and interest on any one topic. Sites lacking an easy-to-follow organization, overly dense layouts, and abundant pop-ups overwhelm the cognitive needs of a user with varying abilities very quickly, causing that person to become frustrated and disengage. Another very common one is associated with navigation and interaction [11]. Most people on the autism spectrum and with other neurodiverse conditions prefer predictability and structure. Websites and apps that have layouts or navigation that do not make sense are overwhelming and hand over difficult tasks, finding the information or tools users want or need. Some dyslexic users will find it hard to read large blocks of text when unformatted, especially in non-reader-friendly fonts [12].

2.3 Best Practices for User-Centred Design for Neurodivergent Individuals

User-centred design should emphasize accessibility and inclusivity, helping to make online environments accessible for those who are neurodivergent through simplification, flexibility and customization. Best practices for making navigation clear and intuitive, avoiding unnecessary distractors that increase cognitive load, providing multiple ways for accessing the content which users may prefer, and personalization features for configuring fonts, colour contrasts, and controlling background noise [13]. Besides this, content should be arranged in such a way that it follows a logical sequence with clear headings and predictable patterns for those who may possess any difficulty with executive functioning or might be becoming overstimulated by the sensory input. Included design should have the potential to allow alternative input methods if deemed necessary, for fine motor control difficulties. Testing with neurodivergent participants and gathering feedback while designing your product will make sure that that product fits their needs and challenges [14].

III. EXISTING TECHNOLOGICAL DEVELOPMENT AND STRATEGIES

Most of these technological developments and approaches involve tracking of time spent on screens, mental health-related prompts to reflect on activities, and tools that reduce distractions or help one control their interference with technology. However, these are usually solutions made more with a neurotypical population in mind, in which other needs like neurodivergent needs, specifically might not have been taken into consideration [15]. For example, they may not be flexible enough for people who require extended time to process information, and focus tools may not reduce the overwhelming sensory inputs that neurodivergent people experience on overcrowded web pages. Although inclusive experience strategies aim at reinforcing healthier tech habits more generally, there still lies a gap in how well these strategies would address the neurodivergent user's requirements [16]. Beyond time constraints, a more comprehensive strategy is required, one that gives neurodivergent individuals choices to personalize their interactions as well as lessen cognitive load.

IV. FOSTERING EMPATHY IN THE DESIGN PROCESS FOR NEURODIVERGENT USERS

For the effective design of online platforms for neurodivergent users, there is a need to infuse empathy in the process. Thereby, one can introduce empathy by encouraging the design team to learn about neurodivergent experiences, their needs and challenges, and allowing them to engage with diverse cognitive profiles through techniques such as user personas, co-design workshops, and immersive simulations that help designers experience how their products can affect neurodivergent users [17]. For instance, simulation of sensory sensitivities may help designers understand just how overwhelming specific choices in design may be. The engagement of neurodivergent people in the design process as consultants or beta testers foregrounds their perspectives when developing a product so that these are developed with greater sensitivity and accuracy to their needs. In the end, more diverse as well as user-friendly interactions are the outcome of empathic design [18].

V. SUGGESTIONS FOR ENHANCING ONLINE ACCESSIBILITY FOR NEURODIVERGENT PEOPLE

Designing settings that are flexible, intuitive, as well as inclusive will be the future of attaining digital accessibility for neurodivergent individuals. These more practical strategies would include design tools such as responsive layouts, content personalization, and sensory-friendly settings. Guidelines could include adherence to WCAG accessibility standards and other content that is presented in formats for accessibility such as text reading for those who might find it easier to read when these are enabled, for example, audio descriptions or closed captions to make things even more accessible [19]. Features the developers should also include "focus modes" which dumb down interfaces for distracted types and tools for controlling sensory stimuli, like switching animations off or lowering the volume. Neurodivergent users will always test it out and continue to evolve it. Beyond that, the potential eventual applications of cross-industry collaboration might express themselves in taking up more generalized best practices in creating online spaces that augment the neurodivergent individual's accessibility [20].

VI. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

6.1 Social Model of Disability

The Social Model of Disability focuses on the idea that disability is actually caused not by the individual impairments themselves, but by societal barriers that exclude people with disabilities. Moving this model into the concept of inclusive experience for neurodivergent users, it hereby highlights the traditional inclusive experience designed for neurotypical users creates barriers that basically limit accessibility and interaction by neurodivergent individuals [21]. Overcoming the barriers listed above, inclusive design to enhance inclusive experience would focus on access, flexibility, and user-centric customization of inclusive experience to suit cognitive differences, thereby addressing exclusion and empowering neurodivergent users to have full connectivity with technology [22].

VII. CONCLUSION

- It is concluded that accessible inclusive experience and inclusion are highly important for enhancing neurodivergent accessibility.
- Facilitative flexible user-centred design strategies and removing barriers to entry can create access through inclusive experience that will benefit society and the economy by their availability but uphold high standards of ethics and law for accessibility.

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